

Osteoporosis in Female Athletes

Review Article

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Abstract

Osteoporosis afflicts millions of women worldwide, but is especially prevalent among female athletes. The stress of intense workouts places these female athletes at a greater risk than the general female population. Absence or suppression of menstruation in female athletes leads to a low peak bone mass and subsequently to the weakening of their bones. This domino effect, coupled with their participation in physical activities, greatly amplifies their susceptibility to stress fractures. Although intense workouts cannot be removed from the regimen of female athletes, increased awareness may prevent or lessen the effects of osteoporosis. Enlightening female athletes on the importance of screening and the methods of diagnosing and treating this condition is the focus of this review.

Keywords: Bone; Bone Mass Density; Osteoporosis; Amenorrhea; Sports; Female Athletes.

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Introduction

Osteoporosis is a condition that affects almost 10 per-cent of the total female population worldwide and is especially prevalent among female athletes. This disease is characterized by a decrease in bone mass and density and enlargement of bone spaces producing porosity and fragility. With the number of women of all ages participating in physical activity steadily increasing, the relationship between osteoporosis and female athletes is a growing concern [1-4]. It is estimated that more than 6 million women now compete in strenuous exercise, worldwide. Despite the benefits of exercise, excessive and strenuous physical activity can have negative effects on the reproductive and skeletal systems, leading to osteoporosis [5,6]

Anatomy And Physiology

The skeleton, comprised of bone attached with various connective tissues, provides the vehicle with which the body can perform its daily tasks. The skeletal system has many functions; it supports and maintains the framework of the body, aids in body

movement, protects internal vital organs, and acts as a mineral reservoir [7,8]. An integral part of the skeletal system is bone. Bone is a dynamic structure, composed of an organic framework embedded in an inorganic salt [7]. This organic framework is 80% cortical (compact) bone that provides rigidity and tensility; the strength and elasticity come from 20% of trabecular (cancel-lous) bones [7-11].

Bone is dynamically involved in a continuous process of formation and resorption, known as the bone re-modeling process [8,10,12,13]. This process is performed by bone remodeling units and basic multicellular units (BMU) [14]. There are two types of cells associated with bone - osteoclasts and osteoblasts. Osteoclasts are involved with bone resorption, whereas osteoblasts are involved with bone formation. Bone remodeling is initiated by the osteoclast [15]. Osteoclasts contain enzymes that infiltrate the bone surface.

When these enzymes are activated, they dissolve the bone surface, forming small erosion lacunae, which contain the osteocyte cells, releasing the inorganic salts [8,16]. Osteoblasts produce proteins of the bone matrix and regulate the rate of bone turnover and formation. Osteoblasts secrete osteoid, the bone matrix [8,10,16] and osteogenin initiates and promotes osteogenesis [16]. The newly formed matrix mineralizes in a span of three months, completing the bone formation process [8]. After reaching maximum bone mass, the bone remodeling process becomes uncoupled. This uncoupling process results in net loss of bone mass density which may lead to osteoporosis [15,17-20].

In female athletes, there is a higher incidence of osteoporosis due to a lower rate of bone accretion, leading to a lower peak bone mass, particularly in athletes with delayed menarche [5]. Studies have reported a lower vertebral Bone Mass Density (BMD) among young amenorrheic athletes than among athletes with regular cycles [21].

Pathophysiology

Osteopenia is reduction in bone volume to below normal levels

due to inadequate replacement of bone lost to normal lysis. Hyperprolactinemia, excessive exercise, stress, under nutrition, and anorexia nervosa are all causes of functional acquired gonadotrophin releasing hormone (GnRH) deficiency and are associated with osteopenia [22]. The common pathophysiology observed in most cases is hypo-oestrogenism due to suppression of the GnRH pulse generator [1].

Irregular menstruations with anovulatory cycles or amenorrhea have negative effects on bone formation and total bone mass. They lead to a lack of estradiol and are associated with inadequate and unbalanced nutrition. This results in severe impairment of bone formation and a net loss of bone mass [23].

Hormones play an integral part on bone mass. Evidence suggests that the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axis (HPT) and the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian (HPO) axis are physiologically related and act together in certain conditions. Specific thyroid hormone receptors at the ovarian level may regulate reproductive function, along with estrogens at the higher levels of the HPT axis. Hyperthyroidism and hyperparathyroidism are also associated with bone loss. Hyper- and hypo- thyroidism can cause menstrual complications. Hyperthyroidism leads to oligomenorrhea, anovulatory cycles and bleeding, while hypothyroidism is mainly characterized by polymenorrhea, in mature women [24,25]. The hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis is crucial for the function of the gonads. Other factors, such as catecholamines exert non-endocrine regulatory influences within the gonads. Catecholamines can alter blood flow, steroidogenesis and gene expression, depending on the target cells [21,26]. Another hormone of major concern that is associated with exercise and which indirectly affects bone loss is oxytocin (Oxt). Oxt acts in the lumbar spinal cord and accentuates the reflex pressor (mean arterial pressure - MAP) and heart rate (HR) responses to static hindlimb contraction. Endogenous Oxt modulates the exercise pressor reflex by its action on Oxt receptors in the lumbar spinal cord, which accentuates sensory nerve transmission from skeletal muscle [27].

Etiology

Osteoporosis is multifactorial. Intrinsic risk factors include ethnicity (Caucasian or Asian), a positive family history, gender, and certain medical disorders, including thyrotoxicosis, Type I diabetes, rheumatoid arthritis, and Cushing's syndrome. Stehman-Breen et.al., reported that black patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD) have a greater BMD and are at a decreased risk for osteopenia compared with whites, independent of renal osteodystrophy. Physicians should consider osteoporosis and the impact of race on BMD when considering bone disease among patients with ESRD [28]. Late menarche, amenorrhea and early menopause are other intrinsic factors for osteoporosis [29]. Extrinsic or modifiable risk factors include estrogen and calcium deficiencies, a sedentary lifestyle, smoking, excessive alcohol intake [30], amount of salt intake [31] and certain medical conditions [30].

Menstrual disturbances have been known to affect female athletes who are vegetarian. The basis for determining if vegetarianism will have an impact on female's energy imbalances associated with body-weight disturbances or exercise, psychosocial and cognitive factors, and dietary components must be evaluated. Some studies suggest that clinical menstrual problems may be more common in vegetarians. A prospective study found that subclinical problems were less common in weight-stable, healthy

vegetarian women. However, the sample does not represent all vegetarian women, and so the results cannot be generalized [32]. In one study investigating the pathogenesis of age-related osteoporosis in Chinese women with low calcium intakes, reported that age-related osteoporosis might be linked with inefficient intestinal calcium absorption and bone remodeling. The Chinese women were found to have potent intestinal calcium absorption [33]. Cigarette smoking is linked to a variety of hormone-related disorders, both benign and malignant, due to its antiestrogenic effect [34]. Osteopenia can cause osteoporosis. A common cause of osteopenia is glucocorticoid administration [22,35]. It is known incidence of atraumatic fractures in patients receiving long term glucocorticoid therapy and is reported to be around 30%-50% [36-38]. Glucocorticoids decrease osteoblast activity and intestinal calcium absorption and may have effects on calcium regulatory hormones [39,40].

Anticonvulsants reduce bone density through their effects on vitamin D metabolism [41-43] and by directly affecting bone turnover [44-46]. Contrarily, Vitamin D is not a factor for premenopausal women who receive incidental sun exposure or consume fortified foods, but supplementation can be considered for others [47]. Other agents associated with causing osteoporosis are corticosteroids, thyroid hormone, antacids containing aluminum, heparin, cancer chemotherapy, tetracycline, isoniazid, and immunosuppressive agents. However, in contrast to osteopenia associated with estrogen deficiency, cortical bone mass is lost in the latter [10]. A hormonal imbalance in athletes leads to osteoporosis and increased incidence of fracture. Athletes have decreased levels of sex hormones, which can cause physiological changes that can lead to bone loss [45,48].

Female athletes are at an increased risk for certain sports-related injuries involving the knee. The differences in sports undertaken and the gender anatomy and structure can contribute to this risk. Baseline level of conditioning, lower extremity alignment, physiological laxity, pelvis width, tibial rotation and foot alignment are all gender differences. Sports like gymnastics and cheerleading create a noncontact environment, but can cause severe knee injuries. In quick stop or cut sports, female athletes have an increased incidence of anterior cruciate ligament injury through noncontact mechanisms [47].

Female Athlete Triad

In 1992, the American College of Sports Medicine coined the term the female athlete triad, which describes a serious, yet preventable syndrome, comprising 3 interrelated components: (a) disordered eating, (b) amenorrhea, and (c) osteoporosis [49]. Young women are under great pressure to achieve or maintain unrealistically low body weight in a short period of time. This is one of the underlying components of the female athlete triad. Adolescents and women training in sports, who emphasize on a low body weight, are at greater risk [50]. The symptoms of the triad and the severity of the disorder should be recognized by the physician [2,51-54].

Amenorrhea And Osteoporosis

Amenorrhea is abnormal absence or suppression of menstruation. It is a common problem for female athletes and may contribute to stress fractures and osteoporosis [55,56]. Amenorrhea decreases bone density at an age when bone formation should still be occurring. Failure to attain sufficient bone density during

the premenopausal years can result in insufficient skeletal mass after menopause when the rate of bone loss exceeds that of bone formation. Primary and secondary amenorrheas are two types of amenorrhea. Primary amenorrhea describes a state in which a female has not experienced menarche by either 16.5 years of age or within 2 years after the development of secondary sexual characteristics. Secondary amenorrhea is associated with the absence of menstruation for greater than 6 months in a woman with previously normal cycles [33].

There are many causes of amenorrhea. The most common is physiologic amenorrhea due to pregnancy or nursing. Causes of primary amenorrhea include anatomic abnormalities, gonadal failure, and conditions of the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian (HPO) axis. Three important causes of secondary amenorrhea are:

(1) Rigorous physical exercise, (2) anorexia nervosa, and (3) use of medroxyprogesterone acetate injection (Depo-Provera) [33]. A direct correlation between exercise and menstrual disorders has been established. However, the mechanism by which exercise disrupts reproductive function remains unknown. Studies have reported that low energy availability rather than inadequate body fat or exercise stress most likely represents the mechanism by which exercise has a negative effect on the HPO axis in female athletes [57]. Pre-pubertal exercise may contribute to the prevention of osteoporosis by increasing BMD; exercise during puberty is correlated with primary amenorrhea and low peak BMD, and exercise after puberty is linked with secondary amenorrhea and bone loss [58]. Evidence suggests that exercise-related menstrual irregularities (ERMI) are produced by a disturbance of the hypothalamic gonadotrophin-releasing hormone oscillator. This disturbance may either be caused by either an insufficient estrogen or progesterone feedback or by an imbalance of opioid peptide and catecholamine activities mediated by GABA, corticotrophin-releasing hormone and insulin-like growth factor-1[59]. Amenorrheic female athletes are reported to have an increase in potential for lipid peroxidation after exercise. This might have a potential association with low levels of E2 [60].

Hypothalamic amenorrhea (HA) is a type of secondary amenorrhea which is frequently observed in women athletes and female anorexics [61]. Body weight, body composition, eating attitudes, and exercise are modulators of the gonadotrop axis [62]. It is a consequence of low dietary intake as observed in two conditions, anorexia nervosa, and intensive exercise. Prolonged mild dieting characterized by a fat restriction could interfere with gonadotropin secretion. However, the gonadotropin deficiency is partial and may be reversible after improving diet and body composition [63]. HA is caused by many factors, such as an interruption in the release of GnRH, which indirectly causes a decrease in the levels of estrogen and progesterone [64]. However, the mechanism by which stress alters GnRH secretion is not thoroughly understood [65]. Women affected by functional hypothalamic secondary amenorrhea do not respond to stress as usual [66,67]. In diabetic female athletes, diabetes has also been linked to secondary hypogonadotrophic amenorrhea. In amenorrheic women with insulin-dependent diabetes, a derangement in HPO axis has been proposed. In a study with GnRH, corticotrophin releasing hormone, metoclopramide, and thyroid releasing hormone tests were performed in 15 diabetic women, 8 amenorrheic (AD) and 7 eumenorrheic (ED). The AD women showed lower plasma levels of LH, FSH, prolactin, oestradiol, androstenedione and 17-hydroxyprogesterone than the ED women. The AD women also had a lower prolactin response TRH and metoclopramide, and lower ACTh and

cortisol responses to CRH, relative to the ED women [68]. This type of diabetes may involve mild chronic hypercortisolism that may affect metabolic control. Stress-induced activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis would increase hypothalamic secretion of CRH, which in turn would inhibit GnRH secretion by increasing dopaminergic tonus, which consequently lead to hypogonadotrophic amenorrhea[68].

Menstrual disturbances in women can have critical effects on the skeletal system. At the lumbar spine, menstrual disturbances are associated with premature bone loss or failure to reach peak bone mass, while appendicular sites is less affected. Trabecular bone is observed to be more sensitive to hormonal stimuli and less responsive to mechanical loading than cortical bone [69]. There have been studies, which show menstrual dysfunction was related to musculoskeletal injuries in women distance runners [70] and ballet dancers, with a prevalence of up to 66%[71]. In addition, half of the athletes were classified as being at risk for developing eating disorders [71]. However, studies show that the BMD of former amenorrheic athletes normalizes following several years of normal menses or use of oral contraceptives, if early intervention is taken [72].

Leptin

Leptin, the product of the obesity gene, is produced in several organs additional to white adipose tissue, including brown fat, and the placenta and fetal tissues. It is a 16-kDa adipocyte-secreted protein whose serum levels reflects the amount of energy stores and is influenced by short-term energy imbalance as well as cytokines and hormones. It binds to specific receptors, altering the expression of hypothalamic neuropeptides that regulate neuroendocrine function as well as energy intake and expenditure. Evidence suggests that leptin may send information to the brain for LHRH secretion and activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis [73]. Leptin may stimulate release of GnRH from the hypothalamus and of gonadotrophins from the pituitary [74]. However, effects of mild dieting on bone mineral density likely suggests an estrogen-independent mechanism for bone loss, and involves some of the metabolic hormones altered through amenorrhea. These hormones play a vital role in modulating bone turnover and bone mineral density [75].

Leptin modulates the secretion of LH, but not the secretion of GnRH-LH [69]. Initiation of puberty in animals and humans has been correlated with rising leptin levels. Normal leptin levels are integral to the maintenance of menstrual cycles and normal reproductive function. Circadian and ultradian variations of leptin levels are associated with minute-to-minute variations of LH and estradiol in normal women [73], the functions involving: inhibiting food intake, stimulation of energy expenditure, and signaling within the reproductive system [76,77].

Women who were anorexic or who participated in strenuous exercise experienced a decrease in leptin levels in response to starvation. Consequently, this resulted in a decrease in estradiol levels and amenorrhea [75]. Leptin levels in females with anorexia nervosa are low and are related to BMI. However, leptin levels in particular female athletes were even more decreased through the amount of low fat storage [78]. Further studies have assessed the relationship of decreased leptin levels with other hormonal abnormalities in anorexia nervosa and reported that leptin is a necessary, but not essential factor, for the resumption of menses in anorexia nervosa patients [79].

Diagnosis

Osteoporosis in female athletes is usually diagnosed incidentally when examining x-rays for an initial fracture.

On X-rays, radiolucency may indicate osteoporosis [10,80] of the appendicular skeleton, portraying cortical thinning and the loss of trabecular bone, especially in the femoral neck. In order for a standard X-ray to detect osteoporosis, 25% to 30% of the bone mineral content must be already been lost [10,81].

Blood and urine content can also be measured for detecting osteoporosis. Bone resorption markers that are released into the bloodstream are excreted into the urine. Markers for bone formation are measured in the serum. Examples include hydroxyproline, calcium, phosphorous, and cyclic AMP. BMD can be measured through invasive or noninvasive methods. Invasive methods include a bone biopsy taken from the iliac crest [82,83] and a histometry which determines the degree of bone mineralization, the quantity and structure of the trabecular bone, the number of active bone cells, and the rates of bone formation and resorption. Double tetracycline-labeled bone biopsies are helpful in evaluating patients with suspected osteomalacia or renal osteodystrophy before interventions, such as surgical parathyroidectomy [84]. Noninvasive methods, such as plain radiographs [10,81-83,85], radiogrammetry [81,83], single photon absorptiometry [81,82], dual photon absorptiometry [81,83,85-87], computed tomography [83,85], quantitative digital radiography [88], nuclear scanning of total body calcium and retention of [87] Tc-labeled pyrophosphate are used. Another very important test is height [89]. It should be measured accurately by a stadiometer. If the difference between how tall the patient perceives to be and the measured amount is greater than 1.5-inches, there is a strong probability that the patient has had an asymptomatic vertebral compression fracture. Vertebral compression fractures are predictive and diagnostic of future fractures [84].

Osteoporosis in women athletes can only be detected incidentally [90]. However, there are certain signs and symptoms that physicians should be aware of. More athletes competing in leanness sports were classified as being at risk of the female athlete triad compared with athletes competing in non-leanness sports [56,91]. Likewise, the Russell's sign should be observed. This sign consists of skin lesions, consisting of abrasions, small lacerations, and callosities on the dorsum of the hand overlying the metacarpophalangeal and interphalangeal joints. These are caused by repeated contact of the incisors with the hand while inducing vomiting. Recognizing this sign can have profound effects on the patient's musculoskeletal system and general health [53,92].

Treatment

Athletes with amenorrhea and who develop fractures easily should be screened for osteoporosis. Treatments include calcium supplementation, salmon calcitonin, estrogen, vitamin D, anabolic steroids, diphosphonates, fluoride, and coherence therapy. The National Institutes of Health Consensus conference recommended 1.5-g of elemental calcium with vitamin D (400-IU per day) for all postmenopausal women [93]. Women older than 65 should take 1.5-g of elemental calcium with 800-g of vitamin D daily [94,95]. The FDA has approved a nasal spray form of salmon calcitonin. The dose is 200-IU per day in one nostril [96]. Calcitonin has been reported to increase bone mass by 5%-20% [97,98]. It should be used for women who are 5 years postmenopausal, have low bone

density and are unwilling to take estrogen. Estrogen replacement therapy reduces the rate of bone turnover and inhibits bone resorption [99,100]. When prescribed judiciously, many female athletes will benefit from the use of estrogen [101]. Raloxifene was approved by the FDA as a selective estrogen receptor modulator. Raloxifene acts as an estrogen agonist in some tissues and an estrogen antagonist in others. 2 years of treatment with raloxifene, at a dose of 60-mg per day, has shown to increase BMD in postmenopausal women. Clinical studies show that estrogen and estrogen-androgen replacement therapies both prevent the development of osteoporosis, as determined by bone mineral density determinations and bone marker analyses. By adding androgen to hormone replacement therapy, bone loss may be prevented and bone formation may be stimulated [102,103]. Biphosphonates can also be used. Biphosphonates are pyrophosphate analogues, in which a carbon has replaced the oxygen in P-O-P, resulting in a P-C-P structure [104]. These are powerful inhibitors of bone resorption. Biphosphonates reduce the absorption activity of osteoclasts or enhance the osteoforming activity of osteoblasts. Biphosphonates create a positive balance of the remodeling cycle, and increase the density of bone mass, lessening the incidences of bone fractures [105]. Alendronate is the only biphosphonate that is approved by the FDA, having the ability to reduce the incidence of fractures [93]. 5-mg of alendronate should be taken to prevent osteoporosis and 10-mg should be taken to treat osteoporosis [95]. Alendronate at 10-mg per day increased BMD at the spine by 6%-8% and at the hip by 4%-6% over a 3 year period, according to studies of postmenopausal women. Stimulators of bone formation include sodium fluoride, calcitriol, PTH, growth hormone, growth factors, prostaglandin, strontium salts and anabolic steroids [106]. PTH prevents bone loss from the proximal femur and total body and increases lumbar spinal BMD in young women with GnRH induced estrogen deficiency [107].

For treatment of secondary forms of osteoporosis, such as steroid-induced osteoporosis, alendronate has been approved in the US [84] and etidronate has been approved in the UK and Canada [106]. Exercise is another effective treatment and several studies with postmenopausal women show modest increases in bone mineral in response to training. It has been suggested that training can be used to improve effects on BMD in postmenopausal females. Bone geometry and mass distribution can be changed as a result of training or hormonal replacement therapy, thereby improving bone strength and reducing fracture risk. Training continues to stimulate increases in bone diameter throughout the lifespan. These types of exercise stimulate increases in bone diameter, diminish the risk of fractures by mechanically counteracting the thinning of bones, and increases bone porosity [108,109]. However, there is no agreement on the quantity, frequency and type of exercise [110,111]. Weight-bearing exercise is recommended three times per week for one-half hour each [109,112]. It should be noted that the patient must commit to the exercise, in order to sustain BMD already gained [96].

Discussion

It is important that women participate in sports and develop skills that promote lifelong athletic participation. However, when one engages in strenuous exercise, serious complications can arise. Disorders, such as amenorrhea, eating disorders and osteoporosis, are common complications that can occur in female athletes [113]. Proper screening, diagnosis and treatment should be accommodated to promote a healthy life-style. More research is needed in the area of female athletes and osteoporosis. However,

er, along with this research, physicians, coaches, trainers, female athletes, and parents need to be educated about the association of athletes and the female athlete triad, with osteoporosis as a crucial component. Detailed history and physical examination provide a great opportunity to detect triad disorders and educate female athletes on the importance of a healthy nutrition, normal menstrual function, and exercise associated with osteoporosis [114]. Delay or failure to recognize and manage these patients may result in the emergence of athletic triad with potential serious consequences of increased stress fractures, scoliosis, and thin body mass.

References

- Constantini, N.W., and Warren, M.P. (1994). Special problems of the female athlete. *Baillieres Clin Rheumatol* 8, 199-219.
- Forsberg, S., and Lock, J. (2006). The relationship between perfectionism, eating disorders and athletes: a review. *Miner Pediatr* 58, 525-536.
- Troy, K., Hoch, A.Z., and Stavrakos, J.E. (2006). Awareness and comfort in treating the Female Athlete Triad: are we failing our athletes? *WMJ* 105, 21-24.
- Andreoli, A., Celi, M., Volpe, S.L., Sorge, R., and Tarantino, U. (2012). Long-term effect of exercise on bone mineral density and body composition in post-menopausal ex-elite athletes: a retrospective study. *European journal of clinical nutrition* 66, 69-74.
- Warren, M.P., and Stiehl, A.L. (1999). Exercise and female adolescents: effects on the reproductive and skeletal systems. *J Am Med Womens Assoc* 54, 115-120, 138.
- Peeters, G., Brown, W., and Burton, N. (2013). Physical Activity Context Preferences in People with Arthritis and Osteoporosis. *Journal of physical activity & health*.
- Adams, M. ed. (1990). *The Skeletal System* (New York: The Benjamin/Cummings Publishing Co).
- Arnaud (1985). Mineral and bone homeostasis. In *Textbook of Medicine*. (Philadelphia: WB Saunders Co), pp. 1415-1423.
- Ganong, L.H. (1963). Review of Medical Physiology. In *Lange Medical Publications*.
- Silverberg, S.J., and Lindsay, R. (1987). Postmenopausal osteoporosis. *Med Clin North Am* 71, 41-57.
- Bartell, S.M., Han, L., Kim, H.N., Kim, S.H., Katzenellenbogen, J.A., Katzenellenbogen, B.S., Chambliss, K.L., Shaul, P.W., Robertson, P.K., Weinstein, R.S., et al. (2013). Non-Nuclear-Initiated Actions of the Estrogen Receptor Protect Cortical Bone Mass. *Molecular endocrinology*.
- Eriksen, E.F. (1986). Normal and pathological remodeling of human trabecular bone: three dimensional reconstruction of the remodeling sequence in normals and in metabolic bone disease. *Endocr Rev* 7, 379-408.
- Frost, H.M. (1979). Treatment of osteoporoses by manipulation of coherent bone cell populations. *Clin Orthop Relat Res*, 227-244.
- Riis, B.J. (1996). The role of bone turnover in the pathophysiology of osteoporosis. *Br J Obstet Gynaecol* 103 Suppl 13, 9-14; discussion 14-15.
- Teitelbaum, S.L. (1993). Bone remodeling and the osteoclast. *J Bone Miner Res* 8 Suppl 2, S523-525.
- Ripamonti, U., Ma, S., Cunningham, N.S., Yeates, L., and Reddi, A.H. (1992). Initiation of bone regeneration in adult baboons by osteogenin, a bone morphogenetic protein. *Matrix* 12, 369-380.
- Ivey, J.L., and Baylink, D.J. (1981). Postmenopausal osteoporosis: proposed roles of defective coupling and estrogen deficiency. *Metab Bone Dis Relat Res* 3, 3-7.
- Nordin, B.E., Need, A.G., Morris, H.A., and Horowitz, M. (1985). New approaches to the problems of osteoporosis. *Clin Orthop Relat Res*, 181-197.
- Riggs, B.L., and Melton, L.J., 3rd (1986). Involutional osteoporosis. *N Engl J Med* 314, 1676-1686.
- Reddy, M.S., and Morgan, S.L. (2013). Decreased bone mineral density and periodontal management. *Periodontology* 2000 61, 195-218.
- Barlet, J.P., Coxam, V., and Davicco, M.J. (1995). [Physical exercise and the skeleton]. *Arch Physiol Biochem* 103, 681-698.
- Miller, K.K., and Klubinski, A. (1999). Clinical review 106: Amenorrheic bone loss. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 84, 1775-1783.
- Wurster, K.G. (1998). [Menstrual disorders in athletes]. *Ther Umsch* 55, 256-261.
- Doufas, A.G., and Mastorakos, G. (2000). The hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axis and the female reproductive system. *Ann N Y Acad Sci* 900, 65-76.
- Scoccia, B., Demir, H., Kang, Y., Fierro, M.A., and Winston, N.J. (2012). In vitro fertilization pregnancy rates in levothyroxine-treated women with hypothyroidism compared to women without thyroid dysfunction disorders. *Thyroid : official journal of the American Thyroid Association* 22, 631-636.
- Mayerhofer, A., Frungieri, M.B., Bulling, A., and Fritz, S. (1999). Sources and function of neuronal signalling molecules in the gonads. *Medicina (B Aires)* 59, 542-545.
- Stebbins, C.L., and Ortiz-Acevedo, A. (1994). The exercise pressor reflex is attenuated by intrathecal oxytocin. *Am J Physiol* 267, R909-915.
- Stehman-Breen, C.O., Sherrard, D., Walker, A., Sadler, R., Alem, A., and Lindberg, J. (1999). Racial differences in bone mineral density and bone loss among end-stage renal disease patients. *Am J Kidney Dis* 33, 941-946.
- McGee, C. (1997). Secondary amenorrhea leading to osteoporosis: incidence and prevention. *Nurse Pract* 22, 38, 41-35, 48 passim.
- Albers, M.M. (1990). Osteoporosis: a health issue for women. *Health Care Women Int* 11, 11-19.
- Burger, H., Grobbee, D.E., and Druke, T. (2000). Osteoporosis and salt intake. *Nutr Metab Cardiovasc Dis* 10, 46-53.
- Barr, S.I. (1999). Vegetarianism and menstrual cycle disturbances: is there an association? *Am J Clin Nutr* 70, 549S-554S.
- Kung, A.W., Luk, K.D., Chu, L.W., and Chiu, P.K. (1998). Age-related osteoporosis in Chinese: an evaluation of the response of intestinal calcium absorption and calcitropic hormones to dietary calcium deprivation. *Am J Clin Nutr* 68, 1291-1297.
- Spangler, J.G. (1999). Smoking and hormone-related disorders. *Prim Care* 26, 499-511.
- Cui, L., Li, T., Liu, Y., Zhou, L., Li, P., Xu, B., Huang, L., Chen, Y., Liu, Y., Tian, X., et al. (2012). Salvianolic acid B prevents bone loss in prednisone-treated rats through stimulation of osteogenesis and bone marrow angiogenesis. *PLoS one* 7, e34647.
- Adinoff, A.D., and Hollister, J.R. (1983). Steroid-induced fractures and bone loss in patients with asthma. *N Engl J Med* 309, 265-268.
- Lukert, B.P., and Raisz, L.G. (1990). Glucocorticoid-induced osteoporosis: pathogenesis and management. *Ann Intern Med* 112, 352-364.
- Rueggsegger, P., Medici, T.C., and Anliker, M. (1983). Corticosteroid-induced bone loss. A longitudinal study of alternate day therapy in patients with bronchial asthma using quantitative computed tomography. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol* 25, 615-620.
- Canalis, E., and Delany, A.M. (2002). Mechanisms of glucocorticoid action in bone. *Ann N Y Acad Sci* 966, 73-81.
- Dent, C.E., Richens, A., Rowe, D.J., and Stamp, T.C. (1970). Osteomalacia with long-term anticonvulsant therapy in epilepsy. *Br Med J* 4, 69-72.
- Hahn, T.J., Scharp, C.R., Richardson, C.A., Halstead, L.R., Kahn, A.J., and Teitelbaum, S.L. (1978). Interaction of diphenylhydantoin (phenytoin) and phenobarbital with hormonal mediation of fetal rat bone resorption in vitro. *J Clin Invest* 62, 406-414.
- Valimaki, M.J., Tiihonen, M., Laitinen, K., Tahtela, R., Karkkainen, M., Lamberg-Allardt, C., Makela, P., and Tunninen, R. (1994). Bone mineral density measured by dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry and novel markers of bone formation and resorption in patients on anti-epileptic drugs. *J Bone Miner Res* 9, 631-637.
- Hamed, S.A. (2011). Influences of bone and mineral metabolism in epilepsy. *Expert opinion on drug safety* 10, 265-280.
- Dietrich, J.W., and Duffield, R. (1980). Effects of diphenylhydantoin on synthesis of collagen and noncollagen protein in tissue culture. *Endocrinology* 106, 606-610.
- Teitz, C.C., Hu, S.S., and Arendt, E.A. (1997). The Female Athlete: Evaluation and Treatment of Sports-Related Problems. *J Am Acad Orthop Surg* 5, 87-96.
- Tudor-Locke, C., and McColl, R.S. (2000). Factors related to variation in premenopausal bone mineral status: a health promotion approach. *Osteoporos Int* 11, 1-24.
- Short, J.W., Pedowitz, R.A., Strong, J.A., and Speer, K.P. (1995). The evaluation of pelvic injury in the female athlete. *Sports Med* 20, 422-428.
- Lambrinoudaki, I., and Papadimitriou, D. (2010). Pathophysiology of bone loss in the female athlete. *Annals of the New York Acad-emy of Sciences* 1205, 45-50.
- West, R.V. (1998). The female athlete. The triad of disordered eating, amenorrhea and osteoporosis. *Sports Med* 26, 63-71.
- Otis, C.L., Drinkwater, B., Johnson, M., Loucks, A., and Wilmore, J. (1997). American College of Sports Medicine position stand. The Female Athlete Triad. *Med Sci Sports Exerc* 29, i-ix. Anderson, J.M. (1999). The female athlete triad: disordered eating, amenorrhea, and osteoporosis. *Conn Med* 63, 647-652.
- De La Torre, D.M., and Snell, B.J. (2005). Use of the preparticipation physical exam in screening for the female athlete triad among high school athletes. *J Sch Nurs* 21, 340-345.
- Feingold, D., and Hame, S.L. (2006). Female athlete triad and stress fractures. *Orthop Clin North Am* 37, 575-583.
- Waldrop, J. (2005). Early identification and interventions for female athlete triad. *J Pediatr Health Care* 19, 213-220.
- Timmerman, M.G. (1996). Medical problems of adolescent female athletes. *Wis Med J* 95, 351-354.

- [56]. Weinstein, Y., and Weinstein, A. (2012). [Energy balance, body composition and the female athlete triad syndrome]. *Harefuah* 151, 97-101, 127, 126.
- [57]. Thong, F.S., and Graham, T.E. (1999). Leptin and reproduction: is it a critical link between adipose tissue, nutrition, and reproduction? *Can J Appl Physiol* 24, 317-336.
- [58]. Bass, S., Pearce, G., Bradney, M., Hendrich, E., Delmas, P.D., Harding, A., and Seaman, E. (1998). Exercise before puberty may confer residual benefits in bone density in adulthood: studies in active pre-pubertal and retired female gymnasts. *J Bone Miner Res* 13, 500-507.
- [59]. De Cree, C. (1998). Sex steroid metabolism and menstrual irregularities in the exercising female. A review. *Sports Med* 25, 369-406.
- [60]. Ayres, S., Baer, J., and Subbiah, M.T. (1998). Exercised-induced increase in lipid peroxidation parameters in amenorrheic female athletes. *Fertil Steril* 69, 73-77.
- [61]. Mikhail, B.I. (1992). Reduction of risk factors for osteoporosis among adolescents and young adults. *Issues Compr Pediatr Nurs* 15, 271-280.
- [62]. Bringer, J., Lefebvre, P., and Renard, E. (1999). [Nutritional hypogonadism]. *Rev Prat* 49, 1291-1296.
- [63]. Couzinet, B., Young, J., Brailly, S., Le Bouc, Y., Chanson, P., and Schaison, G. (1999). Functional hypothalamic amenorrhoea: a partial and reversible gonadotrophin deficiency of nutritional origin. *Clin Endocrinol (Oxf)* 50, 229-235.
- [64]. Hergenroeder, A.C. (1995). Bone mineralization, hypothalamic amenorrhoea, and sex steroid therapy in female adolescents and young adults. *J Pediatr* 126, 683-689.
- [65]. Meczekalski, B., Tonetti, A., Monteleone, P., Bernardi, F., Luisi, S., Stomati, M., Luisi, M., Petraglia, F., and Genazzani, A.R. (2000). Hypothalamic amenorrhoea with normal body weight: ACTH, al-pregnenolone and cortisol responses to corticotropin-releasing hormone test. *Eur J Endocrinol* 142, 280-285.
- [66]. Bruni, V., Dei, M., Morelli, C., Schettino, M.T., Balzi, D., and Nu-volone, D. (2011). Body composition variables and leptin levels in functional hypothalamic amenorrhoea and amenorrhoea related to eating disorders. *Journal of pediatric and adolescent gynecology* 24, 347-352.
- [67]. Gallinelli, A., Matteo, M.L., Volpe, A., and Facchinetti, F. (2000). Autonomic and neuroendocrine responses to stress in patients with functional hypothalamic secondary amenorrhoea. *Fertil Steril* 73, 812-816.
- [68]. la Marca, A., Morgante, G., and De Leo, V. (1999). Evaluation of hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis in amenorrhoeic women with insulin-dependent diabetes. *Hum Reprod* 14, 298-302.
- [69]. Sir-Petermann, T., Maliqueo, M., Palomino, A., Vantman, D., Re-cabarren, S.E., and Wildt, L. (1999). Episodic leptin release is independent of luteinizing hormone secretion. *Hum Reprod* 14, 2695-2699.
- [70]. Beckvid Henriksson, G., Schnell, C., and Linden Hirschberg, A. (2000). Women endurance runners with menstrual dysfunction have prolonged interruption of training due to injury. *Gynecol Obstet Invest* 49, 41-46.
- [71]. Hirschberg, A.L., and Hagenfeldt, K. (1998). [Athletic amenorrhoea and its consequences. Hard physical training at an early age can cause serious bone damage]. *Lakartidningen* 95, 5765-5770.
- [72]. Keen, A.D., and Drinkwater, B.L. (1997). Irreversible bone loss in former amenorrheic athletes. *Osteoporos Int* 7, 311-315.
- [73]. Mantzoros, C.S. (2000). Role of leptin in reproduction. *Ann N Y Acad Sci* 900, 174-183.
- [74]. Chou, S.H., Chamberland, J.P., Liu, X., Matarese, G., Gao, C., Stefanakis, R., Brinkoetter, M.T., Gong, H., Arampatzi, K., and Mantzoros, C.S. (2011). Leptin is an effective treatment for hypothalamic amenorrhoea. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 108, 6585-6590.
- [75]. De Souza, M.J., and Williams, N.I. (2005). Beyond hypoestrogenism in amenorrheic athletes: energy deficiency as a contributing factor for bone loss. *Curr Sports Med Rep* 4, 38-44.
- [76]. Kumar, S., and Kaur, G. (2013). Intermittent fasting dietary restriction regimen negatively influences reproduction in young rats: a study of hypothalamo-hypophysial-gonadal axis. *PLoS one* 8, e52416.
- [77]. Trayhurn, P., Hoggard, N., Mercer, J.G., and Rayner, D.V. (1999). Leptin: fundamental aspects. *Int J Obes Relat Metab Disord* 23 Suppl 1, 22-28.
- [78]. Matejek, N., Weimann, E., Witzel, C., Molenkamp, G., Schwidrigall, S., and Bohles, H. (1999). Hypoleptinaemia in patients with anorexia nervosa and in elite gymnasts with anorexia athletica. *Int J Sports Med* 20, 451-456.
- [79]. Audi, L., Mantzoros, C.S., Vidal-Puig, A., Vargas, D., Gussinye, M., and Carrascosa, A. (1998). Leptin in relation to resumption of menses in women with anorexia nervosa. *Mol Psychiatry* 3, 544-547.
- [80]. Scileppi, K.P. (1983). Bone and joint disease in the elderly. *Med Clin North Am* 67, 517-530.
- [81]. Ayers, J.W. (1985). Hypothalamic osteopenia—body weight and skeletal mass in the premenopausal woman. *Clin Obstet Gynecol* 28, 670-680.
- [82]. Lane, J.M., Wernitz, J.R., Healey, J.H., and Vigorita, V.J. (1986). Metabolic bone disease and Paget's disease in the elderly. Part I: Metabolic bone disease. *Clin Rheum Dis* 12, 49-70.
- [83]. Silverman, S.L., Cummings, S.R., and Watts, N.B. (2008). Recommendations for the clinical evaluation of agents for treatment of osteoporosis: consensus of an expert panel representing the American Society for Bone and Mineral Research (ASBMR), the International Society for Clinical Densitometry (ISCD), and the National Osteoporosis Foundation (NOF). *J Bone Miner Res* 23, 159-165.
- [84]. Miller, P.D. (1999). Management of osteoporosis. *Dis Mon* 45, 21-54.
- [85]. Heath, H., 3rd (1983). Progress against osteoporosis. *Ann Intern Med* 98, 1011-1013.
- [86]. Liu, S.Z., Tian, L.F., Xu, P., Zhuang, G.H., Zheng, F., Tian, J., Ning, Q.L., Zhu, B.F., Lu, S.M., and Yan, H. (2011). Analysis of correlation between blood biochemical indicators and bone mineral density of post-menopausal women. *Molecular biology reports* 38, 939-948.
- [87]. Tsouknidas, A., Anagnostidis, K., Maliaris, G., and Michailidis, N. (2012). Fracture risk in the femoral hip region: A finite element analysis supported experimental approach. *Journal of biomechanics* 45, 1959-1964.
- [88]. Sartoris, D.J., and Resnick, D. (1990). X-ray absorptiometry in bone mineral analysis. *Diagn Imaging (San Francisco)* 12, 108-113, 159, 183.
- [89]. Gunnes, M., Lehmann, E.H., Mellstrom, D., and Johnell, O. (1996). The relationship between anthropometric measurements and fractures in women. *Bone* 19, 407-413.
- [90]. De Cree, C., Vermeulen, A., and Ostyn, M. (1991). Are high-performance young women athletes doomed to become low-performance old wives? A reconsideration of the increased risk of osteoporosis in amenorrheic women. *J Sports Med Phys Fitness* 31, 108-114.
- [91]. Torstveit, M.K., and Sundgot-Borgen, J. (2005). The female athlete triad exists in both elite athletes and controls. *Med Sci Sports Exerc* 37, 1449-1459.
- [92]. Daluiski, A., Rahbar, B., and Meals, R.A. (1997). Russell's sign. Subtle hand changes in patients with bulimia nervosa. *Clin Orthop Relat Res*, 107-109.
- [93]. Hodgson, S.F., Watts, N.B., Bilezikian, J.P., Clarke, B.L., Gray, T.K., Harris, D.W., Johnston, C.C., Jr., Kleerekoper, M., Lindsay, R., Luckey, M.M., et al. (2003). American Association of Clinical Endocrinologists medical guidelines for clinical practice for the prevention and treatment of postmenopausal osteoporosis: 2001 edition, with selected updates for 2003. *Endocr Pract* 9, 544-564.
- [94]. Chang, K.L., Hu, Y.C., Hsieh, B.S., Cheng, H.L., Hsu, H.W., Huang, L.W., and Su, S.J. (2013). Combined effect of soy isoflavones and vitamin D3 on bone loss in ovariectomized rats. *Nutrition* 29, 250-257.
- [95]. Piper, B.A., Galsworthy, T.D., and Bockman, R.S. (1995). Diagnosis and management of osteoporosis. *Contemp Intern Med* 7, 61-68.
- [96]. Epstein, S., and Goodman, G.R. (1999). Improved strategies for diagnosis and treatment of osteoporosis. *Menopause* 6, 242-250.
- [97]. Chung, P.H., Verkauf, B.S., Eichberg, R.D., Casady, L., Sanford, E.J., and Maroulis, G.B. (1996). Electroejaculation and assisted reproductive techniques for anejaculatory infertility. *Obstet Gynecol* 87, 22-26.
- [98]. Reginster, J.Y. (1993). Calcitonin for prevention and treatment of osteoporosis. *Am J Med* 95, 44S-47S.
- [99]. Taichman, L.S., Havens, A.M., and Van Poznak, C.H. (2013). Potential implications of adjuvant endocrine therapy for the oral health of postmenopausal women with breast cancer. *Breast cancer re-search and treatment* 137, 23-32.
- [100]. Seibel, M.J., Cosman, F., Shen, V., Gordon, S., Dempster, D.W., Ratcliffe, A., and Lindsay, R. (1993). Urinary hydroxypyridinium crosslinks of collagen as markers of bone resorption and estrogen efficacy in postmenopausal osteoporosis. *J Bone Miner Res* 8, 881-889.
- [101]. Davis, S. (1999). Hormone replacement therapy. Indications, benefits and risk. *Aust Fam Physician* 28, 437-445.
- [102]. Wires, K.M., Zhang, X.W., Olson, D.A., Turner, R.T., and Iwaniec, U.T. (2012). Androgen prevents hypogonadal bone loss via inhibition of resorption mediated by mature osteoblasts/osteocytes. *Bone* 51, 835-846.
- [103]. Shoupe, D. (1999). Androgens and bone: clinical implications for menopausal women. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 180, S329-333.
- [104]. Gatti, D., and Adami, S. (1999). New bisphosphonates in the treatment of bone diseases. *Drugs Aging* 15, 285-296.
- [105]. Fojtik, Z., and Kandusova, M. (1997). [Bisphosphonates in the treatment of osteoporosis]. *Vnitr Lek* 43, 696-699.
- [106]. Adachi, J.D., Bensen, W.G., Brown, J., Hanley, D., Hodsmann, A., Josse, R., Kendler, D.L., Lentle, B., Olszynski, W., Ste-Marie, L.G., et al. (1997). Intermittent etidronate therapy to prevent corticosteroid-induced osteoporosis. *N Engl J Med* 337, 382-387.
- [107]. Ensrud, K.E., Barrett-Connor, E.L., Schwartz, A., Santora, A.C., Bauer, D.C., Suryawanshi, S., Feldstein, A., Haskell, W.L., Hochberg, M.C., Torner, J.C., et al. (2004). Randomized trial of effect of alendronate continuation versus discontinuation in women with low BMD: results from the Fracture Intervention Trial long-term extension. *J Bone Miner Res* 19, 1259-1269.
- [108]. Suominen, H. (2006). Muscle training for bone strength. *Aging Clin Exp Res* 18, 85-93.
- [109]. Roghani, T., Torkaman, G., Movasseghe, S., Hedayati, M., Goosheh, B., and Bayat, N. (2013). Effects of short-term aerobic exercise with and

- without external loading on bone metabolism and balance in postmenopausal women with osteoporosis. *Rheumatology international* 33, 291-298.
- [110]. Bravo, G., Gauthier, P., Roy, P.M., Payette, H., Gaulin, P., Harvey, M., Peloquin, L., and Dubois, M.F. (1996). Impact of a 12-month exercise program on the physical and psychological health of osteopenic women. *J Am Geriatr Soc* 44, 756-762.
- [111]. Chesnut, C.H., 3rd (1993). Bone mass and exercise. *Am J Med* 95, 34S-36S.
- [112]. Mosti, M.P., Kaehler, N., Stunes, A.K., Hoff, J., and Syversen, U. (2013). Maximal strength training in postmenopausal women with osteoporosis or osteopenia. *Journal of strength and conditioning research / National Strength & Conditioning Association*.
- [113]. Wang, H.L., Tai, M.K., Hung, H.M., and Chen, C.H. (2013). Unique symptoms at midlife of women with osteoporosis and cardiovascular disease in Taiwan. *Menopause* 20, 315-321.
- [114]. Gidwani, G.P. (1999). Amenorrhea in the athlete. *Adolesc Med* 10, 275-290, vii.